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1. Introduction

By describing and analyzing a witoto discourse, I intend to grasp the specific properties of a "rhetoric" at stake in a society which is distinct and different from ours. Being cautious towards an ethno-sufficient attitude which is always at risk, I contrast the witoto rhetoric with the one with which we are intimate in our own cultural tradition. Only then, building on this genuinely ethnographic work — anchored in observable data — shall we proceed to enrich our reflection stuff, our reference corpus, on the basis of which we shall have to broaden or to review our traditional interpretative conceptual frame. Only by acknowledging a socio-cultural alterity (to be explored) do we discover new realities. Our position and our intention thus opposes the comparative rhetoric of G.A. Kennedy. In a culturally diverse corpus of discourse, he identifies the categories of classical western rhetoric and he assimilates the discourse universe of the entire world to phenomena we already know and which proceed from our cultural tradition. I problematize the interpretation of discursive facts, of facts of rhetoric, always by relating them with the culture that produces them. I adopt this method so as to let the culture appear in its specificity and to let the rhetoric appear as a specific product emerging from a given way of life.

Before entering into the matter, I find it useful to say a word on the term "rhetoric", because, as it was used in the outline, it seems to me it presents some potential confusion.

Three orders of facts may lie under the term "rhetoric" :

1. "Rhetoric" is firstly the exercise of language in a sense always meant to be efficient in some way, but which, when this intention becomes too obvious, is perceived as a manipulation and therefore misses its goal. We say then : "He's making rhetoric." It is oral exercise of the *energeia* of language (from which G.A. Kennedy wanted to theorize a comparative rhetoric) which, in my view, is always directional or with an orientation towards personal or social goals. To this exercise, always for one's own hand, I shall refer by the term "discourse". Contrasting with this, I reserve the term "text" to a written document, thence to a discourse which was made visual, whether it be a transcription of an oral source or a written composition.

2. But "rhetoric" also designates the reflection upon, and theorization of the conditions, means, and mechanisms which produce efficiency in discourse; we speak then of the "science of rhetoric"). The products of this theorization effort I will call "explicit rhetoric."

3. A third area remains to be considered : that of the universe of the forms of discourse which are culturally available to the subject and which he uses in carrying out his social roles, his social duties and his personal interests. This universe of discursive forms I will call "implicit rhetoric." In this sense, I claim that the Witoto have an implicit rhetoric, which does not imply that the Witoto have an explicit theory of their discursive practices - although, using the content of some discourses and with an inquiry, one might find a reflection upon language and its uses, but this knowledge is not constituted into a specific body as it is in our "tree of sciences." It would rather be a domain to be constituted by a researcher on the basis of scattered material the entirety of the thought of which is therefore, here also, implicit in the general discursive practice. One might then speak of an implicit witoto rhetoric theory. When I speak of an implicit witoto rhetoric, I mean a set of observable uttered discourses, in which I can differentiate forms which reoccur in defined situations and which, therefore, are as many models which the subjects did internalize within themselves and which they can produce in the relevant social situations. Accounting for this implicit rhetoric requires the researcher to establish an adequate metalanguage. Here a question arises : "adequate to what ? " To the western tradition of rhetorical theory to achieve a scientific status acknowledged by our tradition? or adequate to the Witoto implicit rhetorical theory. This itself, as said, requires from the researcher an effort in explicitation which should start from data which are scattered in witoto oral

comments or glosses. This would also demand the creation of a metalanguage able to reflect how an Amazonian tribal society views rhetorical phenomena.

Such a division into three aspects of the meaning of the term "rhetoric" calls for four remarks which will enable me to situate the rhetorical phenomenon, with respect to language, and with respect to writing.

1. The discursive *energeia*— if we follow Humboldt — can only express itself in the forms and with the contents provided at a given moment in history by a language, better, by a tongue. Now these forms and contents are in turn implicit in the language (tongue), and therefore handled, I wouldn't say unconsciously, but routinely, automatically, by speaking subjects for whom syntactic, grammatical and lexical categories are tacitly obvious matters. Here again, a metalanguage should be established to account for an implicit rationality in morphosyntactic categories and in the structure of the lexicon. This task is usually devoted to grammarians or to linguists. But concerning linguistic description and analysis, one may also wonder whether, generally or most often, linguists have not stopped half-way in establishing interpretative categories without a link to the society and culture which uses them. My hypothesis is that the unity between a language (tongue) and a society (or culture) may be evidenced, on one side, through the discovery of the properties of implicit rhetoric — therefore, the properties of the discourse forms where situational use of the language (tongue) shapes the practical frame for the application of linguistic categories — and, on the other side, by equating the semantic "values" of syntactic structures with social "values" as Karl Lenkersdorf (1996, 1998) attempted to do in his work on the maya tojolabal language and society.

2. The rhetoric science which intends to analyze the conditions and forms of this *energeia* in oral exercise of language is based on writing – and, if it were a paradox, this is but an apparent one. Such a science presupposes the existence in written form of works of the oral language because only so can it take with respect to discourse the distance which is necessary to any theory (at least in the western sense ; the nature of what might be called "theory" in an oral society remaining a field of exploration). In Great Greece as early as the middle of the 7th century BC arose the first nomothetes who instated a law which was public and objectivized. It was probably written, and the first evidence of a written law is known to us through Dracon (621-620) (I thank F. Douay pour for this

indication; cf O. Murray 1995: 196), followed by Solon (590), then by Kleisthenes (507-505)). Therefore, written laws were already available to the sophists of the 5th century who undertook the writing of speeches for commissioners who needed to speak in public in legal cases, political occasions or commemorations. The speeches of the great rhetoricians obviously also reached us in written form, and under that form they were the object of analysis and appreciation during all the time of the elaboration of western explicit theoretical rhetoric.

3. Classical, Graeco-Roman inheritance, appears to bear a determining weight on the way specialists still contemplate the field of explicit rhetoric. In fact, the latter limits himself to institutional social frames such as courts, the political scene and commemorative events. After Aristotle, the poetic use of language is excluded from it, and so is its religious use, although both domains were attested in the Graeco-Roman civilization but they were kept separate from institutional rhetoric.

4. In order to free ourselves from this restrictive inheritance, it may be proposed, firstly, (1) to unite poetics and rhetoric, which were traditionally kept separate, and to add religious rhetoric — by which way we include music, dance and body expression — to come up to problematize one discursive field across different societies, and secondly (2), I propose to ask to what extent language form and language content condition discursive forms (the implicit rhetoric of a society). These two tasks then can help us, I think, (1) to escape western ethnocentrism when facing rhetorical phenomena that are more general and diverse than commonly thought, by questioning the relation between different types of societies and the particularities of their forms of discourse, and (2) they can help us to seek the factors that condition rhetorical forms and to seek them neither in a nebula with little structure or none such as "culture" (as proposed in the outline of this conference), nor in the universe of motivations and finalities which condition classical institutional rhetoric, but rather in a rationality which proceeds from the logics which are implicit in the exercise of human language through discourse in different societies.

When I defined the three acceptations of the term rhetoric, I used two terms which now require further precision. This will give me the opportunity to define the angle from which I regard culture. A while ago I said :

“When I speak of an implicit witoto rhetoric, I mean a set of observable uttered discourses, in which I can differentiate forms which reoccur in defined situations and which, therefore, are as many models which the subjects did internalize within themselves and which they can produce in the relevant social situations.”

The two key terms here are : situation and discourse form, and I borrow them from Bakhtin, for whom the utterance form or the discursive genre – these are two terms he uses – is closely linked to the situation of its enunciation.

Let us quote Bakhtin (1995: 248):

“The use of language results in concrete and singular (oral or written) utterances which belong to the participants in one or another sphere of human praxis. These utterances reflect the specific conditions and the object of each of these spheres, not only for their (thematic) content and verbal style, or for the selection of lexical, sentential and grammatical resources, but also, and primarily, for their composition and structure. The three mentioned components – thematic content, style and composition – depend narrowly on the totality of the utterance and similarly are determined by the specificity of a given sphere of communication. Certainly, each statement is distinct, individual, but each sphere of use of language elaborates its relatively stable types of utterances which we call discursive genres.

The richness and diversity of the discursive genres is immense because the possibilities of human activity is limitless and because each sphere of praxis has a whole set of genres which differentiates and grows as the sphere itself develops and grows in sophistication. The extreme heterogeneity of the (oral and written) discursive genres has to be stressed.”

Bakhtin then provides examples to illustrate what he means by a "set of discursive genres" : brief rejoinders in a daily dialogue, a daily narration, a letter, a military order brief and standardized, a decree, lengthy and detailed, a varied repertoire of bureaucratic reports, public declarations, scientific productions, all the literary genres. In fact, according

to him, all the social manifestations of language can be analyzed as discursive genres, or as we say, forms of discourse.

In another text (Todorov 1981: 289 sqq.), Bakhtin, rather than speaking of "sphere of praxis or sphere of language use," relates the utterance form with the situation by assuming that the situation determines the utterance form. Now the situation, as he understands it, may be taken as culture which produces and reproduces itself, culture in progress, considered at a given moment, that of enunciation which thus is a part of that moment and participates in its form and content.

The two notions – sphere of praxis (or sphere of use) and situation – seem to us not to be identical but both useful. The former evokes "type" situations which occur in a given socio-cultural frame ; for example : chatting with a neighbour in the stairwell, the way a father speaks to his child at a given point of the child's evolution, a speech at a parliament, the report of a football match, or the presentation of a television quiz, and so on. The notion "sphere of language use" has a generic value and is pertinent inasmuch as the set of discourses uttered in such a praxis sphere presents common characteristic features and relationships with the type situation. One such set of utterances may then be characterized as a discursive genre or form of discourse. The notion of "situation" has a specific value and a heuristic function if we succeed in showing how the properties of a particular speech act and the socio-cultural context (including its linguistic dimension) at the moment of its production condition one another. To refer to this specific act, we simply use the term "discourse" which, as I already said, relates to the exercise of language, always meant to be efficient, but always concretely situated in a given situation.

With these preliminary remarks and definitions, we are ready to look at the witoto stuff. I will present a sample of discourse, a sample of speech act, which was recorded in a determined situation.

I distributed before the transcription and translation of a fragment of Witoto discourse: "The Speech of the Tree". I now invite you to listen to its oral performance.

—> listening 10 minutes of the Speech of the Tree, part one.

By taking a closer look at this document (see the annexes), I shall try to show the ways whereby society and culture determine discourse and the ways whereby language shapes discourse.

2. The socio-cultural framework

I shall start with a few general data on the Witoto, this will later help us grasping the cultural references in the discourse. Since the discourse refers to the living environment the data I present concern the traditional way of living ; therefore I shall not cover the current situation. The Witoto live in the Colombian and Peruvian Amazonia and are horticulturists, hunters and fishers. Traditionally, they used to be organized in patrilineal clans, with lines of descendants – 50 to 300 persons – living in multifamiliar houses, called “malocas” in local Spanish (jofa ailoko ; illako in ritual language). Exogamy was practiced not just with respect to the maloca or the clan, but also with respect to a kin group that comprises matrilineal parents up to the third degree. The “chief” (illaima) of each maloca used to be a "feast master" chairing the performance of a series of feasts which evolved by increasing the number of their participants and the ceremonial payments. The Witoto talk then, in Spanish, of a "ceremonial career" which they compare with a professional career in our society. At the end of the career, the ceremonial charge is transmitted preferably to the elder son. This son, in his infancy and youth, was initiated in the ritual performance of language and he was taught the knowledge and know-how wanted for the exercise of his responsibility.

In every feast of the career, two groups of people are confronted : on one side, the inhabitants of the maloca together with those allied to them by marriage coming from other malocas ; altogether they form the group of workers (nakollae) which elaborate the horticultural products — bitter and sweet manioc and peanuts for women, tobacco and coca for men. These products will be exchanged, at the beginning of the dances, against products of hunting brought by the guests (and possibly products of fishing and of recollection of fruits). The latter, non-parents by definition, and resorting from neighbouring

malocas, are led by a feast master who is the ceremonial allied (fuerama) of the host feast master. So guests come to sing and dance for their hosts who listen to them, encourage them and appraise their danced chants. Such ritual services are rewarded with gifts in elaborated horticultural products : cassava associated with other products from the garden : peanuts, tubers, pineapples, and so on, on behalf of women; tobacco paste and juice and coca powder, on behalf of men.

In fact — and here we must enter into the universe of the Witoto way of thinking — the exchange between hosts and guests signifies an exchange between man and the forest, between the feast master as a representative of mankind (with his people called "children" uruki) and the master of the animals who has control over the beings of the forest, the plants and animals, and who is represented by the ceremonial partner (fuerama) and his people. This illustrates an important point in the Witoto view of the world which, for us, is one of the most difficult ones to understand in all its consequences and implications. To make it brief, I would say, first, that the Witoto (as other Amazonian peoples more generally) consider beings of nature, just as human beings, as a part of their society, and second, that the relationship between the natural environment and human nature is transitive. What does this mean ? It means that there are rules of behaviour, modes of communication and exchange, which shape the human behaviour with respect to natural beings, as it does with respect to human beings. But the manifestation of this transitivity is even clearer in a context in which a man may himself become an animal and vice versa : such can be the case, for instance, for a hunter when he does not observe the rules imposed on his activity ; he may then be caught by the animals and move into their world; this is the convert's syndrome which I described elsewhere (Etsa, 1996). It may also be the case of the shaman who changes himself into a jaguar. Conversely, the hunter may find on his way a person (a parent), but one who really is an animal, what he verifies by killing him because the victim then changes back to its animal appearance. I said this is a part of the Indian manner of life, and it is by taking it literally, without questioning its credibility by our standards, that we can understand the Witoto discourse. We must definitely place ourselves within the witoto "logic" derivable from this aprioristic point of view regarding society and nature, which thus are seen together as a form of "socie-ture", to use a properly Witoto form of composition.

Now, what we have just described as actual experiences in present time, and, as we shall see, what belongs to the referential situation of certain forms of ritual discourse (rafue, uai, zomarafue), other forms of discourse — mythical narrations, (bakaki, jaiagai ikak, “stories of ancestors”) and the description of the process of world creation (komuilla uai) — project it in the mythical past. Thus, a gloss I collected on the world creation, tells that Father-Creator created a first world with beings that turned out arrogant and pretended to be equal to the Father, demonstrating no esteem for him. That first world, being bad, was condemned by the Father and eliminated by means of fire. The animals, and with them the entire forest, but also the stars, along with the coal which is found in the underground, are the remaining signs of this first creation and of the original fire. Then the Father made a research, in effort and pain, to finally come up with this world of today which we can see and which is ours. He created the surface of the earth which thereafter will produce domestic plants useful to man. He created the mythical ancestors, and Sun amongst them who, in fact, is the first human being, although endowed with unusual powers. The original Father created domestic plants, those of woman and those of man, and mankind appeared under its two sexed forms, man and woman. To each sex, he gave his own plants to cultivate them and his own tasks. From the first couple, the elder son, the younger son and his sister, then the benjamin of the lineage were born. To each of these original men, a ceremonial career was attributed in the form of a ritual title, each with its own paraphernalia, the three careers being hierarchically ordered following the birth sequence. The life place of this lineage was created : the maloca, in which each son is allocated a defined place where he will live with his family. Starting from then, human beings multiply themselves, and, with them, the malocas. The gloss on creation ends up with the following words of Father-Creator and the final comment which I quote :

“You are living now, nothing misses any more,
for yet domestic plants were created by me,
yet the manioc plant was created by me,
yet the coca shrub was created by me,
yet the tobacco plant was created by me,
Therefore, on your own <hereafter> you shall practice that coca,
you shall practice tobacco.

You shall not sleep”, he said.

“With this, thereafter, you shall seek <knowledge> on your own, and I will speak in your heart from the origin [the East],“ he said.

“This is why you are now as I am.”

Having so said, the Father went to sit in the origin [i.e. in the East].

Henceforward, we are-born-and-live [we form ourselves] so as <we are now>.

The role of tobacco and coca is essential in the exercise of the Witoto language. No Witoto discourse exists without these two accessories, which, as the quoted text says, maintains the daily link with Father-Creator, the daily inspirer of words and acts which have to comply with the witoto social and moral rules. Tobacco is licked as a paste, which is a reduction by cooking of tobacco juice extracted from boiled leaves. This paste is mixed with vegetal salt, extracted from the ashes of some wild plants, so as to make it sweet and peaceful. Coca is consumed under the form of toasted coca leaf powder, which is pounded, blended with ashes of Cecropia leaves and sieved.

For the Witoto, and in accordance with the gloss on creation, human being is fundamentally substance of bitter manioc, feminine substance, but man is in addition substance of tobacco and coca, masculine substance, and the latter generates discourse. Here again, the verb "generate" is to be taken literally. Man, by getting drunk with tobacco paste and coca powder, obtains from the two plants his knowledge, the rules about work and social behaviour ; the plants teach him, show him the way where to drive his life, his activities¹.

The same conception is attested by other Amazonian peoples who take the “ayahuasca“ drink (*Banisteriopsis caapi*), a hallucinogenous plant ; in this case, “ayahuasca” is the species which teaches man directly (Narby 1995). Again we have a relationship, which we qualify social (from teacher to apprentice) between a natural element and a human being. It is a part of what I called the indian "transitivity" between the social world and the world of nature which we, westerners, separate.

Men, who meet traditionally in the maloca during the night to take together tobacco paste (made from time to time) and coca powder (made every night) and talk together, put themselves daily in communication with the Creator, that is, materially with Nature in the form of coca and tobacco, which inspire and teach them the way of life. The figure of the Creator is not that of a particular founder or clan ancestor but rather it signifies the origin of entire mankind, which the feast master, when in ritual position, calls his urukî "his children", - a derived ritual form of the common term urue, "children" also. The same coca and tobacco being a shared attribute of all the Witoto (and of the neighbouring peoples), the same Creator speaks through them in the coca yards of all the clans and malocas. At the same time, speech as generated by tobacco and coca encompasses the world in its totality, but, concretely and particularly, in the terms which evoke and denote the Witoto socie-ture, and this socie-ture manifests itself precisely in its ritual realization which implies the order of the ceremonial careers and which, fundamentally, features the relations between men, in their clanical diversity, and comprising beings of nature, in their specific diversity. It is at the moment, when the men of a residential unit meet together at dusk, in the coca yard, and shift from the daily thoughts and worries limited to their local family universe to a social - or better said : socie-tural - thought, that they also change their daily way of speaking for a ceremonial one. The invocation of the "spirit" of coca and tobacco which contemplates the place of the local group in the whole of the Witoto society and nature, and evokes the relations of the particular maloca with the whole of nature and society may undergo different forms of discourse : informal, formalized, spoken, chanted, whispered, or a hollow whistling, — to list but a sample of the various means used.

Suffice it to remember in what I just said, that daily language is linked with situations of local life in an extended family (lineage), with the interaction between persons living together in a same place and with occasional visitors, parents and "friends", when they merge in this local day-to-day familiarity. But as soon as the whole of society and nature enters the scope of men's thought and speech — and male thought and speech exclusively — , then, thought and speech — this energia I mentioned above — , empowered by the inspiration and the generative power of tobacco and coca, gain a specific form — I call it ritual or ceremonial — which men have learnt how to control, and through which they start interpreting the world and projecting their ritual actions, which precisely are not limited to their social group, but rather concern the whole of the Witoto

society and nature. This shift from daily language to ritual speech, you could clearly perceive in the sample we listened to.

In the light of my own observations during the last thirty years, I should however correct the above statement. Even if Witoto men still meet at nights to talk together while pounding coca powder, taking it and licking tobacco paste, they do not every night achieve the level of ritual communication about society and nature. The ritual order is heavily disturbed nowadays; it is no longer in the foreground of the Witoto thought as it used to be in ancient times (cf. Preuss 1994: 2.704-705). Tobacco and coca, if they now seldom inspire ceremonial discourse, still support a serious conversation in which men express their working experience, commit into cross-collaboration, and plan their future activities. Coca and tobacco then settle a verbal commitment and ensure it will be fulfilled in conformance with the given word. Coca and tobacco also support physical and moral effort, either during horticultural work, or during hunting or fishing, in which communication with nature, which then may be mental only, has a character both propitiatory and preventive. So both ingredients, generators of traditional male speech, still today maintain their function of a spiritual source for all what man undertakes, physically or verbally, following the rules of his society.

3. The situation of the performance.

Having exposed some fundamental features of the Witoto society and culture, we now move on to the specific situation in which the discourse you heard was produced.

By one of those lucky hazards which are the blessing of the anthropologist I attended this discourse in december 1973. Thus the document you heard was not produced by Indians upon the request of the anthropologist, it is rather the testimony of a specific situation, and a properly Indian one, to which an anthropologist who came with the intent of inquiring on horticulture, attended by chance. I visited the maloca of the crane clan, where this discourse was to be delivered, intending to shoot a film sequence on the clearing of a forest. Now, without me being aware of it, the garden for which the forest was to be slashed, right from the start was devoted to the production of future ceremonial payment

during a feast which was to mark the resumption of the ritual activities of the head of the maloca. After some conflicts owing to phenomena which we would call "witchcraft", the feast master had interrupted for some years the feasts corresponding to his career. Now the first step in order to resume a career, consists precisely in clearing the forest to prepare a garden which is why the clearing takes place one year or one year and a half before the day of the feast. But since the result of this work, i.e. the garden, is not intended to the consumption by the local group, but to the future exchange against game with the ceremonial partner and guests, aimed thus at the accomplishment of the rules which create and constantly recreate the Witoto society (still taken in the sense of "societure"), the thought of the protagonists and its discursive expression fits in the ritual level and perspective, because the fundamental intent is from then on geared at the total social event that the feast will be. This is precisely what this discourse, pronounced by the feast master at night, in the eve of the clearing, represents.

At the beginning of the recording, we can hear very clearly the friendly familiar atmosphere in the maloca. The feast master, along with his sons, sits in the coca yard surrounded by women who sit in the perimeter of the maloca and by children who, now come near to the coca yard, and now walk away from it. The yard itself has been set in the left front part of the central space of the maloca. In the yard were laid the recipient for tobacco paste (Ileraki), and the coca powder box from which, all evening long, and during its interruptions, the discourse inspiring resources will be drawn.

Two discourses were delivered that night. The first one which the feast master named "The Word of Tree" (amena uai), was recited in five parts, each separated from the previous one by pauses of varied lengths during which the participants shifted back to the daily language code ; the second one called "The Word of Summer" (fimona uai), was pronounced last and in a single shot.

The subject of both discourses, as derived from the interpretation of their content, were preventive and propitiatory. The first one was to guarantee the good, trouble-free, clearing next day. The second one intended to ensure that summer would be fair after this first

horticultural work so that the slashed vegetation would dry well, to enable an easy burning of the future garden.

The sample you heard is the first part of five in the Word of Tree. In the remainder of my talk, in order to be able to enter into the rhetoric matter without being stuck in superficial and uncontrollable generalizations, I shall limit my analysis to that first part of the Word of Tree and let aside the rest of it, just as I will do also with the Word of Summer.

4. The meaning of the discourse

The first question which arises is : what is the meaning of this piece of speech? what do these words tell ? And such is indeed the curiosity I satisfied in the first place when, on the spot, I started transcribing the discourse and translating it helped by two of the sons of the speaker and supported by the latter. Now, a question closer to the Witoto's motivations underlying this talk, and likewise closer to our concerns as rhetoricians, is rather : What does this speech achieve ? What are these words achieving?

I distributed to you the translation of the text; but the meaning of the words hardly accounts for the actual import of the discourse. Actually, the meaning of the words and the thought they express accompany and support an action which we perceived in the rhythmic panting of the speech which begins slowly and accelerates and intensifies towards the end. Such a panting discourse is obviously a very particular exercise of linguistic *energeia*. Now, its meaning is not just implicit in the event, it is also explicitly evoked in certain of its parts by the language. To this action the following lines refer : 82-83, 100, 106, 111-112 and 117, the last line of the piece. The breath of the origin, that is, that of the Creator, moves upwards, towards here, the present moment, and the speaker, as the Creator, is about to release it. But the explicit key of the meaning is provided by the first line of the second part, in which the speech partner summarizes what just happened : /He (that is to say the speaker) has just released the breath/, whereby the son of the speaker refers to the discourse, to the panting which just ended. Thus the speaker is not just talking about releasing the breath (as the cited lines attest), he actually releases it by rhythmically panting his discourse. The meaning of his words realizes itself in the very speech act, or, to adopt the words of Manfred Bierwisch (1990), meaning is not just

spoken, it is simultaneously shown. In this sense, it can be said that the signifying effect of language — at least in the case we are examining — does not take place through intellectual, moral or emotional processing of the expressed thought, and thence draws neither on logos, nor on ethos, nor on pathos, but by the implication of all the organs involved in the production of voice and by drawing directly on the auditive and visual perception of listeners.

However and simultaneously, it must be acknowledged that the physical manifestation of the breath which realizes the action uttered by the words does have a form, which we may call cultural, since, on the one hand, it is learnt, and therefore transmitted between generations, and realizes itself identically in the same situations, and that, on the other hand, it implies the adequation of thought and language to the rhythm, to the speed and to dialogic exchange.

In addition, the discourse speaks about the nature of this breath and about the intent of this action of releasing and launching the breath. Thus, the breath which is physically manifested in the panting has a quality and a purpose, and these can only be understood in the very living environment and cosmivision of the Witoto people, that is, in the general framework of its culture.

It is said (line 83) that breath is violence, that it is fire, that it is strength and an unforgiving one (i.e. an invincible strength), that it is sun, the paragon of heat (line 111); it is therefore a destructive strength.

This destructive strength is launched against trees and produces shavings, splinters, as we read in lines 84-88, where three species of very hard-wooded trees are mentioned, which sets forth the great strength that is needed to slash them down. The breath of the speaker is then slashing the forest, thus anticipating the action of the next day of the group of men who gathered to listen to the discourse. So this is the nature and intent of the discursive *energeia* manifested simultaneously in speech and breath, by words and by panting.

It should be noted nevertheless that these examples of particularly hard trees are mentioned twice only (lines 84-88 and 42-45, where a fourth species is added). In all the rest of the discourse, the purpose of the action undertaken by the speaker is evoked with other terms, which are understandable only by reference to the Witoto cosmogony, of which we provided a few elements before. As we will see now, the discourse actualizes, in the specific situation given by the project of slashing the forest for a ritual garden, a knowledge which, for the Witoto, exists a priori only under a specific — terminologic, syntactic and rhetoric — discursive form, which we may call a "rhetorical universe of representations". How the discourse establishes references to that global discursive universe, and how it evokes them, by what means, this is what we are going to see now, because it will unravel the singular features of the implicit Witoto rhetoric.

Let us first address the lexicon, the selection of words, and their import :

The first reference to the slashing of trees is made line 10 where it is said that the Father is about to eat. The verb chosen, *ri-*, signifies "to eat meat", as opposed to the verb *gui-* which signifies "to eat in general, and to eat vegetable food in particular". What the Father will eat is the trees, the forest, from the comment which was made to me, and this, line 22 confirms (*/I shall eat that forest/*). Plants being meant here, one would expect the term *gui-*. Now if the speaker uses the verb "to eat meat", it is because he profiles trees as the first mankind, the arrogant and disrespectful one, which the Creator eliminated by fire. "To eat meat" suggests then a cannibal deed associated with violence (see line 37), the violence of war as it used to be ritually carried out by the Witoto up to the beginning of the century. The shift from the plants of today to mythical humans and their assimilation and mutual semantic equivalence, show up in lines 31 and following. The speaker treats trees and creepers as a single bundle of wood, indicating by this diminutive metaphor that it will be easy for him to eat it out. Simultaneously he incorporates violence into himself (line 37) and turns up the surface of the earth, seen as a leaf, and with it this bundle of wood (the forest), thus sending it down to the subterranean world, that is, eliminating it (line 38). Now at that moment, the bundle of trees and creepers is called *uruki*, "children", by the Creator, that is, mankind, but referring to that first mankind which was bad, and against which the speaker unchains his violence. Yet this bad mankind has its own strength : it thunders and

flashes lightening (lines 39, 41). Then we are back to a plant language, the four species of hard trees flash lightening (lines 42-45), but this original mankind knows it is condemned by the superior strength of the speaker, for it starts weeping (line 40). The strength of the Father is such that he just has to look towards that original mankind (line 54) for the beings of the forest to turn sweet (the fierce ant, the scorpion, the biting spider; lines 56-58). By these words, the speaker makes the slashing easy and trouble-free, for instance, free of ant, scorpion and spider bite, that is to say without the hostile strengths of nature hurting man. The strength of the discourse of violence, which is implicit in the choice of terms, in their semantic associations, in their re-evocation of the original creating gesture and in the energy of the rhythmically jerked breath, dominates the adverse forces of a mankind which became nature but, as in the origins, hostile, and therefore to be defeated and eaten or to be sweetened to remove from it its aggressive strength.

From line 68 and on, the idea of eating meat as a metaphor of slashing the forest is reiterated — so there is a rehearsal of the initial theme. It becomes more explicit in its reference to cosmogony, develops in a different direction and goes beyond all what was said so far. The term breath itself will be introduced (line 82).

The original forest (the bundle of trees and creepers) becomes present and current (line 68) in the situation of slashing the forest: leaf-earth shakes, bad mankind and trees whirl and thunder (lines 69-71), as can be heard when a big trunk, when falling, involves all the other ones. The act of eliminating bad mankind through a process of creation comes now in explicit terms which connote the concrete perceptions one has when trees are falling. But soon (lines 72-74), we are again in cosmogony. Children, the first mankind, had been arrogant, but they become poor and they wail. The speaker turns himself into Lord of Violence (Juziñamui), and it is this original mankind which whirls (line 81). Then the original breath is brought back to actuality: the breath of violence, the breath of fire, the breath of invincible strength, the breath of thunder (line 83), which since the origins, frightens (line 85) and cleaves the trees (line 84, 86-88).

The same ideas and the same images are repeated once again: tree-children shake and thunder (line 93), terminate themselves (line 103), the earth shakes and is cleaned (line 107), tree-children become silent and come to nothing (line 114) and finish (line 115). But

this time, the cause of victory over the humanized and adverse natural forces is explicitly the breath that the speaker verbally evokes and also orally manifests by the jerked, rhythmized and accelerated reciting. In fact, following the Witoto conception, breath is vital energy, if not even semen, as mentioned in another discourse. This energy, discursively controlled, positive and productive of life – since the slashing, the clearing, the garden, are a source of life –, prevails over the negative natural forces which simultaneously are also social forces when seen as the beings of the first creation and under the angle of war relations between clans.

There we see how, in a verbally intricate manner, the meaning of discourse plays simultaneously on the cosmologic level of a mythical past and on the technical level of the present. This blending — by particular, stylistic, and vocal rhetorical processes which we shall examine further — of a cosmological narrative dimension, but which thereby loses its narrative character, in a *hic et nunc* enunciative action, is properly the ideological background of ritual discourses. Thence ideology ceases to be the universe of representations, as so often assumed, but it is his practice in daily life when the latter becomes ritual. This ideology might be called "pragmatic" since it has value and meaning only by its integration into action, and since only through action, and in action, do we comprehend its particular form that is specific of the type of society in which it operates. This shift from the quotidian level to the ritual one – I think – is clearly to be perceived when one pays attention to the way voice stress and discourse structure change at the beginning of the record.

However the breath, as a vocal *energeia* which underspans the rhetoric, and as a vital and physical force which overcomes adverse forces and slashes the forest, arises at line 82 only. It springs from what was mentioned on the beginning of the discourse : from tobacco and coca (line 3 and sqq.). The speaker begins with telling the creation of domestic plants, singling out among them tobacco and coca (lines 3-5) and announcing that he will look – i.e. direct his attention, his mind (lines 1-2) – towards what has been given to men, what was left to them, upward, on the earth. Then we are told that he turns himself into coca — assuming into tobacco also (line 8). This identification of the speaker with coca and tobacco is confirmed at line 12 : /The Father starts eating meat, the coca plant starts

eating meat/, meaning trees, i.e. the original mankind. We said it above: men are substance of coca and tobacco, and these two plants teach men and speak through men's voices. As line 13 says: the Creator — and his deputy the feast master — being substance of coca and tobacco, bring, realize *hic et nunc*, the voice of coca, the voice of tobacco. This speech, generated by coca and tobacco, evoked in the form of tobacco juice line 24 and on, is made violent since the speaker says he produces tobacco juice of fire and of violence (lines 25-26). Facing the strength of this speech, trees and creepers are reduced to easy to slash bundles (lines 31-33). The speaker starts practicing coca and tobacco, he obtains visions through fasting and through a disciplined behaviour (line 34), so that coca and tobacco speak through him. But as tobacco juice is that of violence, it is the speech of violence which will dominate and vanquish the forest, the bad original mankind, which is expressed by the word "eat meat" associated with violence (line 37).

Later, an explicit link is made between several — in our concept — heterogeneous elements: between tobacco, as the support of speech, the place from where it is uttered, the maloca, the axe's blade, the bush knife, and finally the means of subsistence which are the result of horticultural work. In the maloca the speaker practices tobacco and coca (line 59). This maloca, by its vaulted form, is equated with the tapir jaw where the tobacco paste container is traditionally laid on; the jaw, in turn, and always on the basis of his geometric form, is equated with the axe's blade, which will eat the forest (lines 60-61). And through this act, the slashing, the pepper pot, a synecdoque denoting our food, is turned upwards and towards our world, and appears to us (line 62). Then, in this pot, the speaker will eat meat, will really eat meat (lines 63,64,66), since the pot, spiced and stuffed with meat, is a part of all Witoto courses and meals. The word "to eat meat" is thus used here in its primary, non figurative meaning. As if it were to stress and summarize all this associative path of thought, line 67 concludes this section with an ellipsis : /Towards the origin of this pepper pot, of this bush knife, I look./ The discursive structures and linguistic mechanisms that use systematically nominal classifiers (as you can see it in the copy of the witoto text) bring all these apparently heterogeneous elements together and equates them.

However the breath, as a violent energy that the speaker releases towards the forest, the adverse humanity, is not announced before line 82. Before the breath, the speech — the speech of violence generated by coca and the juice of tobacco of violence — produces the same effect on the arrogant children: they thunder, throw lightnings and weep (lines 39-45) at the point of being vanquished, eliminated, or softened, losing their aggressivity (lines 55-58).

From these two terms and their order — speech, then breath —, we can begin to explicitate an implicit rhetoric theory of action in the Witoto discursive practice. Speech — that surges from tobacco and coca, and surges thus from natural, socialized elements — is the first effective force that man has been manipulating since the world was created, as in the Witoto conception, the creation itself of the world, or better said: the creation process, was a discursive process, whose memory the Witoto are keeping in form of a special discourse the feast master pronounces in determined situations, and which we have also been able to record. The witoto conception about the origin of the world and the role of speech, corresponds exactly to that which the first verse of the Gospel of Saint John expresses : " In the beginning was the Verb". Now, breath is a component of speech, as is vision or dream, through which coca and tobacco communicate with men. These three items — speech, breath and dream/vision — are the basic concepts on which is founded and from which is drawn the conception of creation and of the structure of Father Creator's discourse; however we cannot cover them here in detail.

According to this theory, speech draws its strength and efficiency, at the same time, from breath and from dream, from vision. Breath is involved in orality, what manifests itself through voice, but it also reveals life in a living organism and his efforts, his productive will, when it accelerates; it is therefore also semen, and vital energy more generally. Vision and dream are inspired by tobacco and coca which generate the content of his speech, its mental substance, which is not conceived as "logos", the historical foundation of our logic and our form of rationality, but which founds another logic, also conceptually and linguistically formal, but underlying another form of exercise of reason as the discourse of the creation reveals, and as some formal and linguistic indices show it in the Speech of Tree.

But before, we must pay attention to the subject of the speech . Who is uttering this speech ? The first answer is, of course, the speaker, the master of feast and maloca, the father surrounded by his sons, wives and children, in short, by all those who will act as workers and hosts when comes the feast, already planned when the speech is performed. Now, it's interesting to watch the changing implications of the pronoun "I" along the speech, which is itself shifting from an everyday meaning to a ritual meaning. The everyday meaning is : "I, father of my extended family, head of the line of my maloca", whereas the ritual meaning is : "I, Father Creator, acting as true Buinaima, Lord of the Bamboo", which is the ritual title of the master of the feast in the zikii or bamboo career. So, the written text begins with a short part in everyday language, where the speaker refers to the audience with "we": /What has been given us, we are looking at ; this has been left us, up here (l.-2)/. So, starting from us, here on earth, we move to the original Father's creative act, and this creative act is creating through speaking, as told in the first word of line 6 *dainano* which means : "having so said", referring to the Father's creation of domestic plants at the line before. The Father as subject of the sentence is maintained in the next one : /Over there, is the origin from where he looked up at us/, and then comes a sentence in the first person : /I shall shape myself as a coca bush/, where "I" represents the Father Creator speaking. So the speaker here is quoting the Father's words. The next lines (9-12) go back to the story of what the Creator has done : /He made himself coca, he made himself an orphan/, which means that he had not yet any family, nor lineage/descent group, nor clan. Line 12 tells: /The Father is about to eat (meat), the coca bush is about to eat (meat)/. Then the speech starts evoking actions in the first person, suggesting that the Father Creator himself is speaking and achieving what his words are saying. It's not before lines 18 and 19 that "I" is clearly identified as the speaker, but the speaker considered in his ceremonial role and called by his ceremonial name : /I am not anybody ; indeed, the Bamboo Buinaima, Lord of the Bamboo, of the origin I am; I am eating; now I am eating; this forest I am eating/, which we find again lines 48-49, 76-77, 94-95 and 109-110. This melting of the speaker and the Creator into one single voice is underlined by the triple coming back of the Father's figure (lines 60, 79 and 99) but, as told line 79, it's to convey the idea that the speaker is shaping himself, actualising himself, both as Father and as Lord of Violence; that is to say, as Father Creator — and as such, father of the extended family of the maloca, responsible for the rites — and as the original Father

invested with Violence, — and as such, protector of his family against threatening evil forces of Nature.

So, we are dealing here with some kind of rhetoric which might be called, at first sight, "religious rhetoric", though it doesn't coincide with what we usually consider as such, I mean prayers, for protection or favour, and epideictic hymns (Chapot & Laurot 2001). The Word of the Tree doesn't address any superior authority, any supernatural or divine being. It is the Creator's word, the original Father's word; but it is not the quotation of divine words as we find in Holy Scriptures or catholic liturgy; here, the divine word is uttered *hic et nunc*. Thus, if we want to approximate the witoto conceptions to ours, we could say that the witoto speaker, while uttering his speech in ritual situation, IS (in fact) god.

But we would be wrong to classify this kind of discourse as purely religious; it's more than that, being also political, social and economic. It's a piece of political discourse because it sets up the master of feast in his ceremonial duty, which, under the title of Bamboo Buinaima, assigns him to the second rank in the ritual hierarchy; claiming the title of Bamboo Buinaima, the speaker openly assumes the nature of his prestige and his position in the socio-natural order he is supporting when he launches the ritual activities with the cutting down of the forest; so he is clearly qualifying the nature of his power. It's also a political speech in relation to the natural component of witoto society, for, while asserting his power over natural beings, the speaker is indeed exerting on them domination and control. But it is a piece of social discourse as well, again in the witoto sense of *socie-ture*, in so far as the speaker addresses at the same time the hearers — members of his broad family he is urging to take part in the planned activities, both productive and ritual — and the natural beings he positions within cosmogony in relation to the present humanity, thus comforting the specific witoto view of *socie-ture*: society-and-nature. Moreover, this speech has an economic significance, for it insures productive work for a ritual exchange to come, and to this work, secures safety and success. So, instead of classifying this kind of discourse as either political or economic or social or religious, according to the a priori categories through which we qualify different domains of activity in our stratified, highly diversified and multi-specialised societies/society, we would give a better account of witoto reality — of a non-stratified society where division of work is restricted to a minimum — by

limiting our distinctions to only two modalities of life, two registers for action and discourse — *cotidianus ac ritualis* — everyday life and ritual; the first one being confined to the restricted circle of life in the residence unit — the *maloca* — with its local preoccupations and interactions; the second one including the whole society with interactions and projects relating the local residence unit to the other units around and to the beings of nature. In fact, what we call political, religious, social or economic, crosses these two registers of life, and it's precisely their particular practical arrangement which poses a problem of interpretation if we are unwilling to assimilate alterity, to reduce otherness to our ready-made categories, and willing, on the contrary, to find a language closely embracing the outlines, and eventually reaching the heart of reality as Indian people experiences it.

The last step we have to make now to complete our demonstration is to show what makes language efficient, as phonic material, in the action stated, and how the mechanisms of Witoto language, the shape of its grammar, conditions Witoto ritual discourse, ritual action, ritual gesture.

If you look at the copy of the Witoto discourse on the hand out you have been given (see annexes), you'll perceive immediately, by sight, without knowing the language, some phonic properties of the speech made obvious by their disposition on the page. Without coming into detail, let's have a quick look at the main devices.

First, we find what specialists of popular poetry — such as Jakobson — call parallelism: the same syntactic structures repeat, but every time they repeat, one word is changed for another. This parallelism comes in pairs, as in phrases 3-4, 5, 9, 13, 32-33, 51-52, 107, 111, 112, 117, etc. ; but it also and often comes in series, as in phrases 3-4, 14-16, 20-22, and especially 42-45, 55-58, 83, 90-92, 100-104. Now, the order of these parallelisms is complex and entangled, because it's often the case that, either a paired parallel is embedded in a serial parallel — see phrases 12-16, 20-22, 28-33, 39-45, 68-71, 84-85, 112-117 — or a serial parallelism is broken off by a non-parallel phrase inserted in between; for instance, between phrases 9 and 11 (both ending with *jaieniki komuilla*), phrase 10 (which does not repeat these words) breaks off the parallel order, but at the same time, it starts a new series (ending with *-rilla*), briefly suspended by phrase 11,

echoing the preceding system. On the reverse, some parallels are doubled; for instance, within the serial parallel (ending with *kue finua*) running from phrases 24 to 27, phrase 26 also repeats the pair of nominal syntagmes of 25, in a reverse order to fulfill the need for some change.

Rime is the second device to stand out. It takes advantage of two different types of final repetition : either repetition of the same word at the end of phrases (see phrases 3-4, 5, 6-7, 8-11, 10-16, 20-22, 24-27, 28-33, 50-52, 55-58, 63-64, 86-88) or repetition of verbal forms ending with identical suffixes (see phrases 6-16, 18-19, 35-36, 38-45, 46-49, 62-65, 67-71, 73-74, 75-76, 80-84, 89-92, 93-95, 99-107, 108-110, 112-117).

The third device, alliteration, also displays two slightly different means: at the beginning of a sentence, it's mainly the repetition, in stressed position, of the same word or syllable; whereas, inside a sentence, we have the same suffix coming back, both means being sometimes combined (see phrases 3-4, 24-29, 31-34, 38-41, 51-52, 59-64, 68-75, 81-84, 85-87, 89-93, 102-108, 112-115).

Actually, we see that the three main devices are superimposed and combined into a tightly woven fabric, which, sustained by the rhythm, produces a rhetoric music we can hardly analyse the means when heard; the written text manages to visualise some of them.

These three devices — parallelism, rime and alliteration — producing phonic impressions on the basis of repetition have for first effect to allow rhythmic energy — cadenced breathing — to lean on articulatory mechanisms so predictable, so well run in, that they can be speeded up in a spectacular way; but they also combine easily with another, more semantic, principle of repetition, the use of those traditional formulae and specific ritual words I have written in italics in my text, which are to be found repeatedly in ritual discourse in general.

The memory who produces the speech seems to lean on a double universe: on one side, a cosmic universe, where the knowledge of cosmogony and the experience of the situation overlap, actualising cosmogony and its projection in present time, the action

projected and initiated by the speech, the cutting down of the forest; on the other side, a phonic universe, which can be called verbal music, organised by rhythm and articulatory gestures repeated under several forms : parallelisms, rimes, alliterations and reiteration of formulae, these four means either alternating or closely entangling to produce precisely this verbal music.

Now, if we were to follow Aristotle's classifications, such an entirely rimed and musically characterised speech would not belong to rhetoric but to poetic. Adopting the criterion of imitation (mimesis) Aristotle puts forth to define what makes the distinctive feature of poetry, we could be tempted to see in the breath and the references to cosmogony an imitation, a discursive representation of the original breath and creative gesture. But such a supposition would be acceptable only if that production of an imitation — this performance — were to have a public watching the represented action. Now, in the ritual situation, all the people there, members of the lineage, are actors implied in the cosmogony gesture and, through it, in the projected work. In a certain way, the situation is closer to those where classical rhetoric is used, when the question is not just to please and touch the soul but also to weigh on decisions that change the fate of people and cities — just as the Word of the Tree influences the fate of men by securing a happy development to their work.

However, an important trend in North-American studies on Indian discourse — Hymes, Urban, Sherzer et alii — assumes the antique qualification, and speaks of verbal art and ethno-poetics, analysing the discourse devices and means as poetic devices and means. But, as in the case mentioned above concerning the terms "political", "social", "religious" and "economic", the wish to apply our categories on witoto discourse doesn't mean much, since it doesn't shed any light on the specific nature, function and functioning, of this type of discourse. Of course, we can assert that in this type of discourse we find devices and means we also meet elsewhere, and namely in our world and history, in productions we are used to call "poems", but nonetheless the function of discourse as action and effect upon reality — forest, work, production — is fundamentally foreign to that mood of pleasure and subtle emotion through which we enjoy poetry. By saying this, I don't mean that no aesthetic thrill is ever felt by people who tell or hear witoto discourse; such an

emotion is certainly one of the components of the situation; but unlike our poetry, it's only one component among others, and not an end in itself as pretended in our saying: "l'art pour l'art".

In the witoto discourse, may it be pleasant and beautiful or not, verbal music as we have described it, is primarily the form and expression of an intentional verbal act meant to produce real effects in the real world; and this attitude primarily pertains to rhetoric.

In the description of the means that produce witoto verbal music, we had no need to study the specific features of witoto language; how they interfere in discourse, how discourse is dependent on them, that's what we are going to look at now.

In order to show how some characteristic features of a language take part in the formation of discourse as action, — verbal gesture rooted in the situation — I have chosen to draw two examples from the witoto verb system.

In witoto language, the morphology of the verb — excepted in the durative mode (-o- durative present vs. -ui-/zoi- durative past) — cannot distinguish present from past (while future is a morphologically marked verbal tense). In witoto language, the only way to refer explicitly to past is to use the adverb *jae*: a long time ago, before. On the other hand, the verb in its predicative function has a choice between two forms : a conjugated form ending with suffixes of persons, and a non-finite form — the "infinitive" — without any mark of person, the "subject" of the action being placed before the verb, in the position of a determinant. So the predicative infinitive functions as a noun, and forms with its ante-positioned subject a nominal group. Between those two predicative verbal forms there is a semantic difference: with the conjugated verb, the focus is on the subject as topic or thema, so we can speak of a thematic assertion; whereas with the infinitive, the focus is on the action, event or state, considered as the setting (Petersen 1994 : 63-65) of the situation; the focus being on the comment or rhema, we can speak of a rhematic assertion..

Now, if you look at the text in witoto, and if I tell you, first, that in all the sentences (except 13, turned in the passive voice) the verb stands at the end; and, second, that the infinitive

form ends with the suffix –lla or –a (truncated under the effect of rhythm and speed when the verbs end in –kei), then you'll realize immediately that in almost all the discourse, assertion is a rhematic assertion, orientated toward action, and placing the hearer in the setting of the action.

The exceptions to this rule are, in their turn, meaningful. When the speaker is stating his ceremonial name to justify his role, then he uses the conjugated form putting the focus on the subject's "I" ; such are the verbal forms ending with –kue (lines 18-19, 35-36, 46-49, 53, 75-77, 93-95 + 98, 108-110). Sometimes, this emphasis on the person of the actor — this topicalisation of the subject — encroaches upon the preceding sentence (line 17) or sentences (lines 28-34), and once upon the following (111); but, as a whole, the uses of these two predicative verbal forms available in witoto are clearly contrasted and clearly related to the assertive attitude the situation requires.

Primarily intended to perform an action — the action of eliminating trees, the wicked original humanity, thanks to verbal gesture, verbal music, word and breath —, the Word of the Tree develops and step by step performs this action in the rhematic mode, immersing the hearer into the present situation of action. This development in action is regularly interrupted by the short mention — in the thematic mode — of the social, ritual, economic and political function of the speaking "I", the feast master under his ceremonial title of Bamboo Buinaima. At this point, the action in which the hearers are immersed with the speaker and urged to participate will be attributed to the feast master — at the same time father of the maloca and Father Creator — and inserted in the socio-natural order of ceremonial careers justifying the speaker's initiative, responsibility and efficiency.

If the witoto speaker must choose between thematic or rhematic assertion, he cannot choose a grammatical tense to place the action he is stating either in the past or in the present time. Whether the action takes place in the past or in the present emerges from the context, unless an adverb makes it clear. Now, it's precisely this neutral position of verbal predicates on time scale that is perfectly adequate to fuse remote time of myth and present time of life into a single perspective. In fact, it's difficult for us to decide whether the verbal forms have to be translated in past or present tense. I have made up my mind

for present time, thinking that this tense better corresponds to the realisation of action as the form of discourse displays it in its smallest details. Besides, with the adverb komo (just) coming back 14 times, the action is definitely placed in the present, or even at the threshold between present and immediate future; however, 8 times we find the adverb jae (before): once at the beginning of the first half of the speech, when the speaker evokes the Creator who, a long time ago, created coca and tobacco, and 7 times in the second half of the speech when an object belonging to the present time is assimilated to its equivalent in the past (lines 62, 84, 87), when the first humanity's bad behaviour and fear is mentioned (lines 72, 74, 85) and when Father Creator is shown again performing his original gesture (line 99). In some way, explicit cosmogony references are made here with this adverb of time, whereas during the major part of the discursive path, this reference remains implicit under an indefinite grammatical tense, where mythic and real time merge, giving the opportunity to state at the same time and as one single event the original gesture and the actual human action.

As it is the case with the two modes of assertion, we see here that a specific feature of this language grammar — lack of differentiation between present and past — allows to state a specific cultural feature: the merging of original time and present time in the discursive ritual action. We could, again and in a short-cut, say that "language is the thought of culture".

5. Conclusion

And now I come to my conclusion.

All the way through, my talk has been about "rhetoric", heard in the first meaning I had defined at the beginning : "the practice of language, always meant to be efficient in some way..." — so a steadily interested, motivated, intentional practice of language, which I referred to with the word "discourse". I have tried to describe this practice in a particular and concrete situation in the midst of witoto society, but without calling a priori on our categories, coming from our explicit rhetoric theory, itself drawn from the analysis of this practice in our midst : western societies, institutions and history. I have made obvious, I

hope, through the characteristics I have described, that witoto discourse does not belong to deliberative genre, nor judicial, nor even epideictic. But at the same time, this discourse does belong to rhetoric, in so far as it is pretending to act upon its hearers, bringing them confidence and safety in the action to undertake, and act upon the beings of Nature it dominates and tames; it also belongs to rhetoric in the second meaning defined at the beginning — "reflection upon the means that make discourse efficient" — since the practice of language implies a conception, a theory of language and of its components as efficient tools for action, or even tools to create some reality, some world; without excluding the poetic dimension of this discourse where verbal music is definitely an implement.

We can also claim that witoto discourse is relevant to logos in so far as it takes place on one hand in a narrative cosmogonic logic, and on the other hand, in a taxonomic logic ordering the world and its forces — its inherent energy to be controlled and handled by man — the achievement, the full arrangement of which is expressed in the Word of Father Creator we had the opportunity to hint at. Witoto discourse also implies and expresses ethos, insisting on the social and ritual charge taken by the speaker and on his authority and responsibility towards the local group, from the maloca people to the whole society. And as well, witoto discourse arouses pathos, moving affects, when it evokes hostile fiend forces the speaker faces and fights with violence, and which, in some other context, may provoke war, whereas in the present case they are defeated and swept away to the benefit of fruitful gardening, which means life and, in a ritual perspective, feast, joy and mirth to come, celebrating food abundance and bounty.

In our talk, we have tried to demonstrate that witoto discourse has at the same time a political, social, economic and religious significance, since its scope and efficiency reaches all four domains.

Then, it becomes obvious that none of the attributes classical rhetoric science uses is able to give an exhaustive account of witoto discourse nor classify it under a well-known rhetoric genre. For all these attributes only consider and highlight some aspects of witoto discourse, bringing them back — or reducing them — to those categories familiar to our knowledge.

So, it seems to me that the only way to provide witoto rhetoric as such, in its specificity, with an adequate theory, is to acknowledge a witoto pragmatic ideology. To grasp this pragmatic ideology, we must observe the varied yet culturally limited and specified situations of discourse where language works as action — or, more exactly if we want to stick to witoto thought, as "creation" —; and the shapes and forms language then assumes, we must describe, as powerful implement, in situ, in relation to witoto socio-cultural situations, rites and practices, including witoto language itself.

Relying on our demonstration, we can now easily claim (with our hosts in Mainz): that "culture emerges from and is sustained in rhetoric". However, I feel that what makes the witoto case interesting is not accounted for in so general a statement. To me, what makes the witoto case interesting is the fact that it questions harshly our traditional conceptual system, exhibiting its limitations, weaknesses and rigidities, opposing to our cognitive universe a more discursive universe, so far from us, so strange indeed, that we have some trouble to conceive it precisely ; to bridge the gap, we need to meet this strangeness, "de-westernise" our minds, and, may be, forge new concepts for a de-colonised rhetoric culture.

That's what — for right or wrong — I have dared propose before you.

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ANNEXES:

A fragment of a witoto discourse: "The Word of the Tree" (Amena Uai)
(Colombia, Amazonas, Igaraparaná, clan aimeni "heron", december 1973)

The presentation of the text puts in evidence the repetitions, parallelisms, alliterations and rimes.

Every number is a phrase.

In italics appear the repetitive formulae and frequent words that are specific of the ritual discourse, not only in the present case, but also in others.

Points <...> signify repetitions and interjections, "jii", from the speaker and his dialogic partner.

In black letters appear classificatory suffixes.

Underlined are the nominal syntagms.

At the end of phrases, forms that end in -lla, -kei<lla>, -nei<lla> and -a are non finite, nominal, verbal forms; these endings make visible the groups of rhematic utterances that contrast and alternate with those of thematic utterances ending in the personal suffix -kue.

1 Kairi igano afenomo kai erokeilla.

2 Ja kai ari kaimo fienokeiga.

3 Niinori jibina komuilla.

4 Niinori diona komuilla
riaroki komuilla.

5 Jaka niinona jae moo riaroki komuitari
jibina komuitari.

6 Dainano jillakimona ari erokeilla.

7 Niino jillaki nabefuena ari erokeilla.

8 Kueka jibinana komuilla.

9 Kai moo jeilla meinona... bifokoni... moo komuilla
jaieniki komuilla.

10 Akie izei eroikana moo ririlla.

11 Jaieniki komuilla.

12 Moo ririlla
jibina ririlla.

13 Akie izei eroikana kue atika jibina uai
diona uai...

14 Komo... kue ririlla...

15 Moodikue ririlla.

16 Birena kue ririlla...

17 Komo... nabefuena... riridikue...

18 Buñedikue...

19 Nabefuena iko jillaki zikida buinaimadikue...

20 Kue ririlla...

21 Komo kue ririlla

22 Birena kue ririlla...

23 Ikue bie izei eroikana komuilla...

24 Kueka bibi llerabi kue finua...

25 Juziña llerabi...

reiki llerabi... kue finua...

26 Komo... kue finua...

reiki llerabi...

juziña llerabi...

27 Llerabi...ja kue finua...

28 Bibi jillaki... finodikue...

29 Nabefuena... komo... bibina...finodikue...

30 Beno... finodikue...

31 Biki... finodikue...

32 Biki amena iki... jillaki... finodikue...

33 Biki... raue iki... jillaki... finodikue...

34 Nabefuena... bikina... finoritikue...

35 Kueka... buñedikue...

36 Nabedi... zikida... buinaimadikue...

37 Komo... ririlla... juziña... komuilla...

38 Bikina... bibe... dobeirikeilla...

39 Llazika... biki... uruki... jillaki... ninomo... giririkeilla...

40 Llazika... uruki... eebikeilla...

41 Llazika... bikimona... boribikeilla...

42 Nabefuena... kiringomona... boribikeilla...

43 Ameo... teiñomona... boribikeilla...

44 Feigimona... boribikeilla...

- 45 Obereimona... boribikeilla...
- 46 Komo... atidikue...
- 47 Nabefuena... biki... jillakimo... erokeilla...
- 48 Buñedikue...
- 49 Nabedi... zikida... buinaimadikue...
- 50 Ririlla...
- 51 Bikina... ririlla...
- 52 Birena... ririlla...
- 53 Komo... atidikue...
- 54 Nabefuena... bire... jillakimo... erokei...
- 55 Llazika... biki... uruki... jillaki... ninomo... naimenei...
- 56 Omoki... naimenei...
- 57 Akaido naimenei...
- 58 Joma naimenei...
- 59 Daanomo... bikomo... finori
- 60 Dakode... biko... iziko...
mooma... iziko...
- 61 Bikodo... ririlla...
- 62 Llazika... biko... jae... monifue... daina... illiko... nabefuena... keifo.. dobaiñokei..
- 63 Illiko... bikomo... ririlla...
- 64 Illikomo... ririlla...
- 65 Erokei...
- 66 Komo... nabefuena... ririñe...
- 67 Biko... illiko... bifei... kuefei... jillakimo... nabefuena... erokei...

68 Llazika... ari... nabefuena... biki... jillaki... jirenoikei...

69 Llazika... bibe... nabefuena... feianoikei...

70 Llazika... uruki... jillaki... ninomona... kaverikei...

71 Uruki... jillaki... ninomo... giririkei...

72 Llazika... jae... abi... inoti...

73 Uruki...dani... duere... zefuiñe...

74 Uruki... keilliñe... jae...

75 Llazika... atidikue...

76 Buñedikue...

77 Nabedi... zikida... buinaima...

78 Ririñe...

79 Kueka... moonaa... komuilla... Juziñamuina... komuilla...

80 Jii... erokei...

81 Llazika... nabefuena... uruki... jillaki... ninomona...giririkei...
kaverikei...

82 Llazika... ari... nabefuena... jagilli... jillaki... jirenoikei...

83 Juziña... jagilli...

reiki... jagilli...

llaroka... jagilli... jillaki...

ameue... jagilli... jillaki... jirenoikei...

84 Llazika... nabefuena... jae... bibiki... jillaki... kuinoikei...

85 Jae... jarede... daide...

86 Kiritingo... ibiki... kuilla...

87 Jae... feigi... ibiki... kuilla...

88 Oberei... ibiki... kuilla...

- 89 Llazika... nabefuena... komeki... eizikei...
- 90 Llazika... nabefuena... ninomo.. ibiki... jillaki... ninomona... giririkei...
- 91 Llazika... nabefuena... jagilli... jillaki... kue zuitakei...
- 92 Llazika... uruki... jillaki... ninomona... kaverikei...
giririkei...
- 93 Llazika... komo... atidikue...
- 94 Buñedikue...
- 95 Nabedi... zikida... buinaimadikue...
- 96 Ririñe...
- 97 Erokei...
- 98 Akie... izei... eroikana... atidikue...
- 99 Komo... nabefuena... jae mooma... erokeilla...
- 100 Izei... eroikana... nabefuena... jagilli... jillaki... jirenoikei...
- 101 Ninomona... jagilli... jillaki... zuitaiki...
- 102 Llazika... komo...ninomona... jagilli... jillaki... ninomona... giririkei...
kaverikei
- 103 Llazika... uruki... jillaki... ninomo... Ilikei...
- 104 Llazika... uruki... jillaki... ninomo... giririkei
- 105 Llazika... kue jeruiñei...
- 106 Nabefuena... jillaki... dinena... ari... zuitaiki...
- 107 Llazika... bibe... eiño... jogobe... bibe... ninomo... kue tetenogana...ñefikei...
ninomo... jufenogana...ñefikei...
- 108 Llazika... komo... atidikue...
- 109 Buñedikue...
- 110 Nabedi... zikida... buinaimadikue...
- 111 Atika... reiki... jagilli...
jitomai... jagilli... jillaki... zuitadikue...

112 Llazika... komo... nabefuena... kuekoni... zuijikei...

kuekoni... jirekei...

113 Uruki... jillakimo... erokei...

114 Llazika... uruki... jillaki... ninomo... lliikei...

ninomo...uruki... tainokei...

115 Llazika... uruki... fuiraikei...

116 Erokei...

117 Akie izei... eroikana... jagilli... jillaki... jirenoikei...

jagilli... jillaki... zuitaikei...

(END OF THE FIRST PART)

(BEGINNING OF THE SECOND PART)

118 MD: Ja jagilli e faia.

119 CD: Akie izei eroikana amena uai.

120 Jae akie izei eroikana einamaki amena uai jillaki atide.

121 Jillaki uai zuitade.

122 Akie izei eroikana itino jillakimo komo ari kai erokei.

123 Jae mei bu afeno uibiñoi.

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Traduction of the witoto discourse: "The Word of the Tree" (Amena Uai)

1. PART ONE

1 CD: What was given to us, this we're going to look at.

2 To us this was granted up

3 Over there <in the garden> coca forms itself.

4 Over there is where tobacco forms itself, where sowed plants form themselves.

5 For over there is where the Father before created sowed plants, where he created coca.

6 After so said [=so done] from the origin, he looked upward [to us].

7 Over there is the origin and he looked upward [to us]

8 "I myself will form myself as coca"

9 After our Father went away, in this house [in the coca yard] the Father formed himself, he formed himself as an orphan.

10 So in this manner the Father is going to eat [meat].

11 He <the Father> formed himself as an orphan.

12 The Father starts eating, the coca plant starts eating <the trees>

13 "So in this manner I brought the voice of coca, the voice of tobacco".

14 "I shall just eat"

15 "Being the Father I shall eat"

16 "This forest I shall eat"

17 " Verily, I shall just eat"

18 "I am not anyone"

19 "Verily, I am the Bamboo Buinaima of the origin"

20 "I shall eat"

21 "I shall just eat"

22 "I, in this manner, will form myself."

23 "This forest I shall eat"

24 "I am the one who makes this tobacco juice [tobacco paste]."

25 "The tobacco juice of violence, the tobacco juice of fire, I make them."

26 "I am just making them, the tobacco juice of fire, the tobacco juice of violence."

27 "The tobacco juice, I make it."

28 "The origin of this juice, I make."

29 "Verily I'm just making this juice."

30 "Here, I'm making <it>."

31 "This bundle I'm making."

32 "The origin of this bundle of trees, I'm making."

33 "The origin of this bundle of creepers I'm making."

34 "Verily, just like into coca, i'll make myself into tobacco."

35 "I 'm not anyone."

36 "The true Bamboo Buinaima of the origin, I am"

37 "I shall just eat [meat] <and> become violence."

38 Just like this bundle of <trees [bad people]> - this leaf [-earth] turns itself down.

39 In this moment, the origin of the children of this bundle is slashing down in thunder.

40 In this moment, the children start out weeping.

41 In this moment this from this bundle it flashes with lightning.

42 Verily it flashes with lightning from 'palisangre' (kiritingo).

43 From the ameo teiño tree ("lightning cough"), it flashes with lightning.

44 From the red tree (feigi) it flashes with lightning.

45 From the 'charapilla' (obérei) tree it flashes with lightning.

46 "I'm just bringing."

47 "Verily I am looking towards the origin of this bundle."

48 "I am not anyone."

49 "The true Bamboo Buinaima of the origin, I am"

50 "I shall eat [meat]."

51 "This bundle <of trees> I shall eat."

52 "This forest I shall eat."

53 I'm just bringing

54 Verily, towards the origin of this forest he is/I am looking.

55 In this moment the origin of the children of this bundle <from nothingness> turns sweet.

56 The 'conga' ['isula' = fierce ant] turns sweet.

57 The scorpion turns sweet.

58 The joma spider turns sweet.

59 In this same place, in this maloca, he is learning [experimenting].

60 This same maloca is this jaw, the jaw of the Father [the place of the tobacco juice = the edge of the axe]. One and the same is the angle of the maloca and the jaw of the Father and the edge of the axe.

61 With this jaw, he will eat.

62 In this moment, that pot, the pepper pot of the aforementioned food, he turns it up.

63 "Pepper pot, in this pot I shall eat [meat]."

64 "In this pepper pot I shall eat."

65 "Look !"

66 "Verily, I shall just eat."

67 "Verily, towards the origin of this pepper pot of this knife I'm looking."

68 Verily, in this moment the origin of this bundle [of trees] moves upwards.

69 Verily, in that moment this leaf [-earth] shakes.

70 In this moment the origin of the children simply whirls.

71 The origin of the children simply thunders.

72 In that moment, before they were arrogant.

73 The children became miserable again.

74 The children screamed before.

75 In this moment I am bringing <the origin of the the Bamboo Buinaima>.

76 "I am not anyone."

77 "I am the Bamboo Buinaima."

78 "I shall eat [meat]."

79 "I myself will form myself as father, I will form myself as Juziñamui [the Lord of Violence]."

80 "Yes, look !"

81 In this moment, verily, the origin of the children thunders <from nothingness>. It whirled.

82 In this moment, verily, the origin of breath moves upwards.

83 The origin of the breath of violence, of the breath of fire, of the breath of unforgiving strength (llaroka), the origin of the breath of lightning, moves.

84 In this moment, verily, the origin of this cleft of before, cleft itself.

85 Before, "It's frightening", he said.

86 The cleft of 'palisangre' (kiritingo) is falling.

87 The cleft of the red tree (feigi) is falling.

88 The cleft of 'charapilla' (oberei) is falling.

89 In this moment, verily, the heart runs away.

90 Verily in this moment, over there the origin of the cleft thunders <from nothingness>.

91 Verily in this moment, the origin of breath I shall release.

92 In this moment the origin of people[-trees] <from nothingness> shakes and thunders.

93 In this moment I shall just bring.

94 "I am not anyone".
95 I'm the true Bamboo Buinaima."
96 "I shall eat [meat]."
97 "Look !"
98 "Thus, in this manner, I shall bring."
99 "Verily the Father of before looked."
100 Thus in this manner, verily, the origin of breath moves.
101 <From nothingness> the origin of breath releases itself.
102 In this moment, <from nothingness> the origin of breath thunders and shakes <from nothingness>.
103 In this moment, the origin of people [-trees] stops [finishes] <from nothingness>.
104 In this moment, the origin of people [-trees] thunders <from nothingness>.
105 In this moment I shall not forgive <it>.
106 "Verily, from the side of the origin I will release (the breath) upward".
107 In this moment this leaf [-earth], the surface of Mother's breast, shall <from nothingness> be emptied and shaken by me, it shall be cleaned by me.'
108 In this moment I'm just bringing.
109 "I am not anyone".
110 "I'm the true Bamboo Buinaima."
111 "The breath of fire brought <by myself>, the origin of the breath [wind] of the sun I shall release."
112 In this moment verily, it shall just be released by me, it shall just shall be moved by me."
113 The origin of people [-trees] he looks into.
114 In this moment the origin of people [-trees] <from nothingness> stops [becomes silent], <from nothingness> people [-trees] comes to nothing.
115 In this times, people [-trees] finishes.
116 Look !
117 Thus in that manner the origin of breath moves, the origin of breath releases itself.
>>>

2. BEGINNING OF THE SECOND PART

118 MD: He just threw the breath.

119 CD: So in this manner is the Word of the Tree.

120 Before in this manner the ancestors brought the origin of the Word of the Tree.

121 They released the words of the origin.

122 The origin being in this manner, we just shall see upward.

1On this point, see the narration of Knera in Echeverri 1993: p. X

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